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To the problem on vacuum structure

Annotation

It is proposed such vacuum structure that follows **only** from solutions of Maxwell's equations, i.e. any additional suppositions are not allowed. Casimir's effect is explained on the framework of the proposed vacuum structure.

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1. Introduction

The vacuum structure is studied by quantum field theory, which does not tire of presenting it as very complex structure. Indeed, this theory does not offer anything consistent with the concepts of classical physics to describe the structure of a vacuum.

It is offered below some structure that follows **only** from a solution of Maxwell's equations without any extra propositions.

In Section 2, it will be proved (as a solution of Maxwell's equations) that it can exist a wave-AND-particle (WAP) representing a cubic volume of a vacuum, in which a volumetric standing wave pulses. It is important to state that this volume has neither physical boundaries nor the boundaries formed by some environmental inhomogeneity. The WAP does not radiate across the faces of the cube but on each edge there is some electric field strength, the vector of which is directed perpendicular to this face.

The values of energy, frequency, and strength at the faces of the cube are some functions only of the size of the cube. There exists obviously the

smallest volume of the cube that can be determined by minimum of energy quantum.

Many these WAPs can occupy the space entirely, without gaps. Namely such structure is described below. Such structure is actually met in nature [4]: the square waves at the sea surface are shown in Figures A and B. However, let's treat the structure and properties of the WAPs at first.

Fig. A.

Fig. B.

2. Typification of waves-and-particles

So, in [1] it is proposed a model of wave-AND-particle (WAP) that will be applied here. For the reader convenience, let's introduce below a concise description of this model.

The strengths of both the electric and magnetic fields found as solutions of Maxwell's equation can be written in the following forms:

$$E_x(x, y, z, t) = e_x \cos(\alpha x) \sin(\alpha y) \sin(\alpha z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (1)$$

$$E_y(x, y, z, t) = e_y \sin(\alpha x) \cos(\alpha y) \sin(\alpha z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (2)$$

$$E_z(x, y, z, t) = e_z \sin(\alpha x) \sin(\alpha y) \cos(\alpha z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (3)$$

$$H_x(x, y, z, t) = h_x \sin(\alpha x) \cos(\alpha y) \cos(\alpha z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (4)$$

$$H_y(x, y, z, t) = h_y \cos(\alpha x) \sin(\alpha y) \cos(\alpha z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (5)$$

$$H_z(x, y, z, t) = h_z \cos(\alpha x) \cos(\alpha y) \sin(\alpha z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (6)$$

where $e_x, e_y, e_z, h_x, h_y, h_z$ are the constant amplitudes of the functions, α, ω are some constants. These amplitudes are coupled by the following equations:

$$h_z = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$h_y = -h_x, \quad (8)$$

$$h_x = -\frac{\varepsilon\omega}{\alpha} e_x, \quad (9)$$

$$e_y = e_x, \quad (10)$$

$$e_z = -2e_x \quad (11)$$

And they can be determined for a fixed value of the parameter e_x . Also, the angular frequency is

$$\omega = c\alpha\sqrt{4.5}. \quad (12)$$

These equations describe a volumetric standing wave that exists inside the cubic volume with the following edge length:

$$L = \pi/\alpha. \quad (13)$$

For this wave, the density of electromagnetic energy is

$$W = \varepsilon E^2 + \mu H^2. \quad (14)$$

Also, the following condition must be fulfilled for this wave:

$$U = \varepsilon |E^2| = \mu |H^2|. \quad (15)$$

The total electromagnetic energy of the wave in the cube is

$$W_o = U \cdot L^3. \quad (16)$$

Note that this energy **does not change in time**.

The coordinate components of the density of energy flow can be written down as follows:

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S_x \\ S_y \\ S_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_y H_z - E_z H_y \\ E_z H_x - E_x H_z \\ E_x H_y - E_y H_x \end{bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

Let's treat the following expression:

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_y H_{\bar{z}} - E_z H_{\bar{y}} \\ E_z H_{\bar{x}} - E_x H_{\bar{z}} \\ E_x H_{\bar{y}} - E_y H_{\bar{x}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17a)$$

We note that

$$\cos(\alpha x) = \cos\left(\alpha \frac{L}{2}\right) = \cos\left(\alpha \frac{\pi}{2\alpha}\right) = 0. \quad (17b)$$

Therefore, the strength components, for which the cosine of a certain coordinate occurs in the definition of functions (1)-(6) on the face perpendicular to this coordinate, are equal to zero. As a result, formula (17a) contains crossed out components of the electric and magnetic fields' strengths that depend on cosine of the corresponding coordinate. It is clearly seen that the components in (17a) are equal to zero. Therefore, the following condition is fulfilled on all faces of the cube:

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_y H_z - E_z H_y \\ E_z H_x - E_x H_z \\ E_x H_y - E_y H_x \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

This means that **the cube does not radiate energy**.

On each face of the cube there is such magnetic field strength, the vector of which is perpendicular to this face. For instance, vector (4) located on the face perpendicular to the x -axis (see also formula (13)) is equal to

$$H_x \equiv \sin(\alpha x) = \sin\left(\alpha \frac{L}{2}\right) = \sin\left(\alpha \frac{\pi}{2\alpha}\right) = 1, \quad (19)$$

So, the energy flow does not come out of this face. However, there is a magnetic field strength perpendicular to this face. A similar conclusion can be made about the other faces of the cube.

Figure 1 shows the magnetic field strengths outgoing from the faces of the cube. It is important to note that in this case the strength H_z is absent due to condition (7) but shown in Figure 1. For the faces located at the negative values of the coordinates, the strengths are directed towards the negative values because there is $\sin(\alpha x) = -1$.

The energy flow does not come out of the face perpendicular to the x -axis. However, the flow circulates along this face because the components S_y and S_z of the flow density do not equal to zero on this face. For instance, $S_y = E_z H_x - E_x H_z$ in (17). Here there are $H_z = 0$,

$E_z \neq 0, H_x \neq 0$ in (19). Therefore, $S_y \neq 0$. In this face similar to the whole volume there is an energy with density U that does not change in time. Therefore, on this face and moreover **on all faces there continuously exists some pressure** equal to the density U .

The above-considered type of WAP can be designated as **WAP-1**.

Fig. 1.

Using an analogy to the results obtained in [1], it is natural to treat another solution for Maxwell's equations. This solution is differed by the way that the following form of solution instead of solution (7)-(11) is used:

$$e_z = 0. \quad (28)$$

$$e_y = -e_x, \quad (29)$$

$$e_x = -\frac{\mu\omega}{\alpha} h_x, \quad (30)$$

$$h_y = h_x, \quad (31)$$

$$h_z = -2h_x. \quad (32)$$

Similar to the previous case, conditions (18) are also fulfilled on all faces of the cube, i.e. **the cube does not emit energy**. On each face of the cube there is a magnetic field strength, the vector of which is perpendicular to this face. The difference is that the strength H_z is also present, since condition (32) is fulfilled in this case.

Similar to the WAP-1 and WAP-2, it is possible to consider two other solutions of Maxwell's equations. The peculiarity of these two

solutions is that the following components of the magnetic and electric field strengths are exploited instead of components (1)-(6):

$$H_x(x, y, z, t) = h_x \cos(\alpha x) \sin(\alpha y) \sin(\alpha z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (41)$$

$$H_y(x, y, z, t) = h_y \sin(\alpha x) \cos(\alpha y) \sin(\alpha z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (42)$$

$$H_z(x, y, z, t) = h_z \sin(\alpha x) \sin(\alpha y) \cos(\alpha z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (43)$$

$$E_x(x, y, z, t) = e_x \sin(\alpha x) \cos(\alpha y) \cos(\alpha z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (44)$$

$$E_y(x, y, z, t) = e_y \cos(\alpha x) \sin(\alpha y) \cos(\alpha z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (55)$$

$$E_z(x, y, z, t) = e_z \cos(\alpha x) \cos(\alpha y) \sin(\alpha z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (46)$$

Fig. 2.

It is easy to see that new solutions can be obtained from the old ones by replacing the notations E and e with the notations H and h , and Vice versa. The fundamental difference will be that the electric field strengths will appear instead of magnetic field strengths coming out of the cube perpendicular to the faces. This is shown in Figure 2.

To draw Figure 1, the following assumptions were used: at some initial moment of time, the phases of sine-functions of time defined by expressions (1), (2), and (3) were equal to zero but the ones defined by (4), (5), and (6) were maximum. Figure 1 shows the direction of the vectors of the magnetic field strengths namely for this moment of time. Such WAP

can be called the WAP with a phase of $\varphi = 0$. Let's assume that this corresponds to the initial value of $e_x > 0$.

The results graphically shown in Figure 2 were obtained in the assumption that at some initial moment of time, the phases of sine-functions of time defined by expressions (1), (2), and (3) were maximal but the ones defined by (4), (5), and (6) were equal to zero. Figure 2 shows the direction of the vectors of the electric field strengths namely for this moment of time. Such WAP can be called the WAP with a phase of $\varphi = \pi/2$. This corresponds to the initial value of $h_x > 0$.

Extra four variants of WAPs can be obtained by using the values of $e_x < 0$ and $h_x < 0$ at the same moment of time. In this case, the vectors of the strengths must be directed inside the face but not outside the face of the cube.

Table 1 lists all the variants of the WAPs.

Table 1

WAP	Formulas for E and H	Initial data	Formulas for e and h	Figure	Strengths
1	(1)-(6)	$h_z = 0$ $e_x > 0$ $\varphi = 0$	(7)-(11)	Fig. 1	$H_z = 0$ $H_{x,y} > 0$
					Asymmetric WAP. The H -vectors are directed outside the cube
2	(1)-(6)	$e_z = 0$ $h_x > 0$ $\varphi = \pi/2$	(28)-(32)	Fig. 1	$H_{x,y,z} > 0$
					Symmetric WAP. The H -vectors are directed outside the cube
3	(41)-(46)	$e_z = 0$ $h_x > 0$ $\varphi = \pi/2$	(7)-(11)	Fig. 2	$E_z = 0$ $E_{x,y} > 0$
					Asymmetric WAP. The E -vectors are directed outside the cube
4	(41)-(46)	$h_z = 0$ $e_x > 0$ $\varphi = 0$	(28)-(32)	Fig. 2	$E_{x,y,z} > 0$
					Symmetric WAP. The E -vectors are directed outside the cube
5	(1)-(6)	$h_z = 0$ $e_x < 0$ $\varphi = \pi/2$	(7)-(11)	Fig. 1	$H_z = 0$ $H_{x,y} < 0$
					Asymmetric WAP. The H -vectors are directed inside the cube

6	(1)-(6)	$e_z = 0$ $h_x < 0$ $\varphi = 0$	(28)-(32)	Fig. 1	$H_{x,y,z} < 0$
	Symmetric WAP. The H -vectors are directed inside the cube				
7	(41)-(46)	$e_z = 0$ $h_x < 0$ $\varphi = 0$	(7)-(11)	Fig. 2	$E_z = 0$ $E_{x,y} < 0$
	Asymmetric WAP. The E -vectors are directed inside the cube				
8	(41)-(46)	$h_z = 0$ $e_x < 0$ $\varphi = \pi/2$	(28)-(32)	Fig. 2	$E_{x,y,z} < 0$
	Symmetric WAP. The E -vectors are directed inside the cube				

3. Vacuum structure

Let's consider now a set of WAPs. The cubic form of WAP allows us to assume that a set of WAPs forms a continuous volume. This is shown in Figure 3. For this case, a WAP with a phase of $\varphi = 0$ and a WAP with $\varphi = \pi/2$ must alternate in all directions of space.

Different combinations of WAPs are also possible.

A space can exist that is filled with WAPs creating only magnetic field strengths on the faces or only electric field strengths on the faces.

A space can also exist that is filled with only symmetric WAPs or only asymmetric WAPs. In the latter case, there should be a space direction in which there is no any strength in any direction. Such a vacuum must somehow exhibit anisotropic properties.

We can assume that nature uses all the variants and there are heterogeneous spaces.

Thus, each WAP remains autonomous but together they form a continuous volume of a vacuum.

It can be assumed that all the WAPs have the same volume and then there is a single vacuum frequency. It can also be assumed that there are different areas of space with different (but common for certain area) volume of WAPs. Then these regions must have different frequencies of a vacuum.

Some face of WAP may be on the border of an empty area of space. Then there will be strength on the border of this area, namely the strength that is present on the specified border of WAP. This strength is the certain strength that forms the standing wave, see notes after formula (11). Thus, the strength on the cubic face of some WAP generates a standing wave in

an empty space and thus creates a new WAP. In this way, **WAPs multiply**, filling the entire vacuum. We can assume that the universe originated from a single WAP.

Fig. 3.

4. Casimir's effect

Consider the right-side lateral surface of the vacuum fragment in Figure 3. Assume that this surface is the boundary of the WAP region. On the open surfaces of the WAPs, at the center of the surfaces there are shown the field strengths' vectors entering and exiting these surfaces. The thick line wrapping around the ends of these vectors conventionally depicts a wave of strengths on the open surfaces. These strengths change sinusoidally over time. Thus, there is a standing wave of the strengths on the surface of the border of the WAP region.

It is very important to state that on the open surfaces of the WAPs there continuously exists some the pressure U mentioned above. If a body is adjacent to these surfaces, it must experience this pressure. Thus, a body in a vacuum filled with WAPs experiences a vacuum pressure from all sides. Each area of WAP also creates pressure on the neighboring area. Therefore, WAP seeks to fill internal voids. Following Torricelli, it can be argued that "a vacuum does not tolerate emptiness".

The pressure gradient in a continuous array of WAPs is determined by the following formula:

$$g = \frac{2U}{L}, \quad (47)$$

where U, L are the pressure on the faces of the cube and the length of the cubic face, respectively, defined in [1]. As a result, some change in the pressure at certain distance A in a vacuum is

$$\Delta p_o = g \cdot A. \quad (48)$$

Taking this into account, we will place two parallel mirror surfaces at a small distance from each other. They can start move closer to each other by the pressure of an infinite number of WAPs outside the plates and move apart by negligible pressure (2) of internal WAPs. And therefore, the pressure of external WAPs should bring the mirrors closer together.

The reader has already grasped that what has been said is the proposed explanation of the Casimir effect, namely there is an attraction of two parallel mirror surfaces located at short distances in a vacuum.

In the existing model of a vacuum [2], Casimir's effect is caused by *"some energetic oscillations of physical vacuum due to continuous creation and annihilation of virtual particles in it... This happens due to the fact that only standing waves can exist in the space between the plates, the amplitude of which is equal to zero on the plates. As a result, the pressure of virtual photons from the inside on two surfaces is less than the pressure on them from the outside, where the birth of photons is unlimited."* In addition, the explanation of this effect recognizes the existence of negative energy [3].

These references are given in order to note the obvious contradiction between the proposed theory (PT) and existing theory (ET).

In the proposed theory, it is proved that there is a volumetric standing wave with certain strengths at the nodes. In the existing theory, it is stated that the amplitude of the strengths at the nodes (on the plates) is equal to zero (it can be proved that the law of conservation of energy does not hold.)

The proposed theory proves that the real particles fill a vacuum, and the existing theory assumes the existence of virtual particles, the birth of which is not limited and the disappearance of which is inexplicable.

In the proposed theory, it is proved that there is a constant vacuum pressure on bodies. In the existing theory, it is assumed that such pressure is created by waves of virtual particles that constantly arise and disappear.

In the existing theory, the existence of negative energy is proved, and in the proposed theory, respect for the law of conservation of energy is preserved.

The reader is asked to choose what the reader likes best.

References

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